

AMINO DERIVATIVES OF TITANIUM TETRABROMIDE. PART II

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Amino derivatives of titanium tetrabromide have been prepared by the action of titanous bromide on some aromatic secondary and tertiary amines, and their properties and structures studied.

The preparation and properties of the compounds formed by the action of titanous bromide on some aromatic primary amines have been studied in a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 838), which shows that though the co-ordination number of titanium in these compounds is only four, but they are fairly stable. The work has been further extended to study the action of some aromatic secondary and tertiary amines on titanium tetrabromide under similar conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amines used were of Merck's or B.D.H. 'extra pure' quality. Titanium tetrabromide was prepared by the method of Olsen and Ryan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 2215), redistilled at 230° and extracted with ether which was distilled over metallic sodium.

General Method of Preparation.—In all the cases, except those mentioned below, the solution of amine in ether was added to the ethereal solution of titanous bromide with constant stirring. When the requisite quantity of the amine solution was added, a precipitate settled down. It was stirred well, kept for about an hour, filtered quickly and washed with ether till the washings did not give any precipitate with titanium tetrabromide. In the case of dimethylaniline and quinoline, the ethereal solution of titanous bromide was added to the amine solution in order to obtain a crystalline precipitate, as a pasty mass, which was not converted into a crystalline precipitate, was formed when the process of addition was reversed. The precipitate was dried over calcium chloride, analysed, and the properties of the compounds studied. Duplicate experiments were carried out in each case. The results reported in the tables are the average of the two values.

Estimation.—Bromine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's method, nitrogen by the Dumas method and titanium as TiO_2 . In all the compounds except tetraquinolino-titanous bromide, amine was also estimated by the potentiometric method and the percentage of nitrogen in the compound calculated. From Table I, the percentage of nitrogen obtained by this method appears to compare well with the results obtained by the Dumas method in all the compounds except tetradimethylanilino-titanous bromide, where a low value is obtained, due evidently to the hygroscopic nature of the compound.

Estimation of Amine by Potentiometric Method.—About 200-350 mg. of the compound was weighed out accurately, dissolved in alcohol and a few c.c. of H_2SO_4 (dil.) added to remove the slight turbidity due to hydrolysis of the compound, and the volume

made up to 100 c.c. A portion of the solution (10 c.c.) was pipetted out in a beaker and to it were added 2*N*-H₂SO₄ (10 c.c.) and *M*/2-KBr. It was then titrated by KBrO₃ (0.1*N*) at the room temperature. When KBrO₃ was added to the solution, it was consumed and there was a gradual change in potential, but near the equivalence point a sudden jump in the potential due to a slight excess of the reagent (free bromine) was observed in all the cases.

As some of the amines examined formed dibromo and others, tribromo derivatives under similar conditions, a blank experiment was carried out in each case with the pure amine under identical conditions (only the graph for diphenylamine is shown: vide Fig. 1, curve IV).

The curves I, II, III and V in Fig. 1 and the curves VI-X in Fig. 2 refer to the estimation of the amine in tetra (-methyl-, -ethyl-, -benzyl)- anilino-, tetra-diphenylamino-, tetra (-dimethyl-, -diethyl-, -benzal-, -dibenzyl)-anilino-, and di-*p*-aminodiethylanilino-titanic bromide respectively

TABLE I
[T.B. denotes titanic bromide]

Compound.	Wt. of the compound.	Wt. of the amine Calc	Wt. of the amine Found (from the curves).	% Nitrogen.
Diphenylamine	0.2292 g.	0.2292 g.	0.2296 g.	8.30
Tetra-methylanilino-T.B.	0.2338	0.1257	0.1253	7.01
„ -ethylanilino-T.B.	0.2842	0.1614	0.1611	6.56
„ -benzylanilino-T.B.	0.3520	0.2342	0.2345	5.01
„ -diphenylamino-T.B.	0.3006	0.1946	0.1937	5.34
„ -dimethylanilino-T.B.	0.3152	0.1791	0.1707	6.27
„ -diethylanilino-T.B.	0.2462	0.1522	0.1518	5.79
„ -benzalanilino-T.B.	0.3134	0.2078	0.2089	5.16
„ -dibenzylanilino-T.B.	0.2952	0.2208	0.2201	3.82
Di- <i>p</i> -aminodiethylanilino-T.B.	0.2562	0.1207	0.1199	7.99

TABLE II

Compounds of titanium tetrabromide with aromatic secondary amines. *

Amines.	Compound formed.	Colour	M.P.	% Titanium.		% Bromine.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Methyl-aniline	Tetramethyl-anilino-T.B. [Ti(PhNH.Me) ₄]Br ₄	Light yellow	236°	5.86	6.03	39.86	40.20	6.92	7.04
Ethyl-aniline	Tetra-ethyl-anilino-T.B. [Ti(PhNH.Et) ₄]Br ₄	Dirty white	242°	5.62	5.63	37.24	37.56	6.37	6.57
Benzyl-aniline	Tetra-benzyl-anilino-T.B. [Ti(PhNH.CH ₂ Ph) ₄]Br ₄	Leafy green	167°	4.28	4.36	29.24	22.09	5.12	5.09
Diphenyl-amine	Tetra-diphenyl-amino-T.B. [Ti(^{Ph} Ph>NH) ₄]Br ₄	Yellowish white	226°	4.46	4.63	30.52	30.89	5.28	5.41

* No compound was formed with carbazole.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

TABLE III

Compounds of titanium tetrabromide with aromatic tertiary amines.

Amines.	Compound formed.	Colour.	M.P.	% Titanium.		% Bromine.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Dimethyl-aniline	Tetra-dimethyl-anilino-T.B. [Ti(PhNMe ₂) ₄]Br ₄	Light grey	139° (decomp.)	5.58	5.63	37.24	37.56	6.38	6.57
Diethyl-aniline	Tetra-diethyl-anilino-T.B. [Ti(Ph.NEt ₂) ₄]Br ₄	White	248°	5.02	4.8	33.02	33.20	5.64	5.81
Quinoline	Tetra-quinolino-T.B. [Ti(C ₆ H ₄ < CH:CH N:CH) ₄]Br ₄	Brownish grey	122°	4.41	5.43	35.82	36.20	6.21	6.33
Benzal-aniline	Tetra-benzal-anilino-T.B. [Ti(PhCH:N Ph) ₄]Br ₄	Deep yellow	160°	4.38	4.40	29.16	29.30	5.04	5.13
Dibenzyl-aniline	Tetra-dibenzyl-anilino-T.B. [Ti{Ph.N(CH ₂ .Ph) ₂ } ₄]Br ₄	Ash grey	154°	3.24	3.29	21.81	21.92	3.86	3.84
<i>p</i> -Amino-di-ethyl-aniline	Di- <i>p</i> -amino-di-ethyl-anilino-T.B. [Ti(Bt ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂]Br ₄	Black	305°	6.86	6.90	45.84	45.98	8.14	8.05

DISCUSSION

The compounds formed with titanium tetrabromide and the secondary and tertiary amines are in many respects similar to those formed with the primary amines. They are generally insoluble in organic solvents, but the compounds formed with diphenylamine, benzalaniline, dibenzylaniline, quinoline and *p*-aminodiethylaniline are soluble in chloroform, absolute alcohol and acetone, and insoluble in carbon tetrachloride, benzene and petroleum ether. Contact with water, sodium hydroxide or sodium carbonate sets in their hydrolysis, but complete hydrolysis takes place only when warmed at about 50° and titanium hydroxide is precipitated according to the equations:

On heating alone they afford a sublimate, which is soluble in water, acidic and responds to the test for Br, : NH in secondary amines and N: in tertiary amines. The presence of secondary and tertiary amines was also confirmed in the aqueous extract by the standard methods. When they are heated with sodalime, the corresponding amines separate out and condense in the cooler parts of the tube, analogous to the behaviour of the compounds with primary amines (*loc. cit.*). The compounds formed

with dimethylaniline and quinoline and titanous bromide are very hygroscopic and begin to decompose on exposure. However, they are fairly stable at room temperature when kept in vacuum or in the perfectly dry air.

Di-*p*-aminodiethylanilino-titanous bromide is hygroscopic, but like the compounds formed with the primary diamines (*loc. cit.*) is very stable, and melts at a high temperature. It hydrolyses only after prolonged boiling with water or alkalis, which seems to be due to the formation of the chelate compound.

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